

occurring in minor amounts such as quartz, feldspar and chlorite are listed in the last three columns (columns 3 to 5). There was a general tendency for the proportion of illite to increase with the depth of the profiles. There was complete absence of feldspar in type II soils.

The results of X-ray analysis found confirmation from the results of chemical analysis of the clay fractions of the soils.

The percentages of SiO_2 , Fe_2O_3 and Al_2O_3 did not show abnormal variations in different clays. The percentage of K_2O varied from 2.70 to 4.58. The high potash content⁵ was indicative of the presence of illite as the dominant clay mineral in almost all the profiles. Except in some layers of profile II, the magnesia content⁶ was also high which suggested the presence of montmorillonite or chlorite in the soils. The low values of cation exchange capacity (8 to 30 meq/100 g clay), however, ruled out the presence of any large amounts of montmorillonite and could be attributed to the illitic minerals. This fact found confirmation in silica to sesquioxide ratios which varied from 2.54 to 5.6 (except in the upper layer of profile II where it was 7.95). The silica alumina ratios⁷ further confirmed the presence of chlorite and illite in the different profiles. The trend of the molar ratios of different profiles at varying depths pointed to the presence of almost the same type of clay minerals in the different soils of Aligarh district though their proportion varied. From the results of X-ray and chemical analyses it was apparent that the clay minerals were associated with an appreciable amount of non-clay mineral matter.

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Azo Dyes. Part IV. 1-Isonicotinoyl-3-methyl-4-substituted-phenylazo-5-pyrazolones

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IN continuation with our interest in this series of compounds few more ethyl α -substituted phenylazo acetoacetates and 1-isonicotinoyl 3-methyl 4-substituted phenylazo 5-pyrazolone dyes have been prepared (column 2, table 1), and tinctorial properties of pyrazolone dyes on wool, silk, acetate silk, terylene, and nylon fabrics were investigated as per methods described earlier¹. The shades of the dyes

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TABLE I—ETHYL α -SUBSTITUTED-PHENYLAZO ACETOACETATE AND 1-ISONICOTINOYL 3-METHYL 4-SUBSTITUTED-PHENYLAZO 5-PYRAZOLONE DYES

(Analytical data, R_f -values and fungicidal properties)

No.	Compound ⁺⁺	Colour	m.p. [°]	yeild %	R_f -values		Amt. in millimoles for complete inhibition
					EO ₂ H : H ₂ O 8 : 2	BuOH:AcOH:H ₂ O 8 : 2 : 5	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1.	C ₆ H ₅ -R ^{**}	light yellow	85-6	92	0.89	0.95	—
2.	2,Cl, C ₆ H ₄ -R	yellow	65-6	80	0.90	0.94	—
3.	3,Cl, C ₆ H ₄ -R	yellow	85	76	0.91	0.95	—
4.	4,Cl, C ₆ H ₄ -R	yellow	82	91	0.91	0.95	—
5.	3,Cl, 2,CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₃ -R	yellow	87	90	0.92	0.95	—
6.	5,Cl, 2,CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₃ -R	dirty yellow	125	87	0.91	0.95	—
7.	2,3,Cl ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R	light yellow	84	98	0.86	0.92	—
8.	2,4,Cl ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R	deep yellow	132	84	0.85	0.91	—
9.	2,5,Cl ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R	light yellow	122	81	0.91	0.91	—
10.	2,6,Cl ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R	dirty yellow	82-3	79	0.91	0.91	—
11.	3,4,Cl ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R	orange yellow	96	81	0.90	0.90	—
12.	2,CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄ -R	yellow	58	80	0.93	0.85	—
13.	3,CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄ -R	yellowish orange	59	79	0.95	0.89	—
14.	4,CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄ -R	light yellow	83	92	0.93	0.91	—
15.	2,CH ₃ , 4,NO ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R	yellow	148-9	86	0.86	0.98	—

NOTES

TABLE 1 (Contd.)

No.	Compound ⁺⁺	Colour	m.p. ⁼	yield %	<i>R_f</i> -values		Amt. in milli- moles for complete inhibition
					EtOH : H ₂ O 8 : 2	BuOH:AcOH:H ₂ O 8 : 2 : 5	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
16.	4,CH ₃ , 3,NO ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R	deep yellow	110-11	82	0.86	0.98	—
17.	2,COOH, C ₆ H ₄ -R	yellow	164	83	0.91	0.94	—
18.	3,COOH, C ₆ H ₄ -R	deep yellow	177	84	0.84	0.93	—
19.	4,COOH, C ₆ H ₄ -R	yellow	203	76	0.84	0.91	—
20.	4,SO ₃ H, C ₆ H ₄ -R	orangish yellow	above 360	79	0.41	0.21	—
21.	C ₆ H ₅ -R ^{**}	deep yellow	225-6	95	0.78	0.91	0.1628
22.	2,Cl, C ₆ H ₄ -R ^{**}	deep yellow	Sint. 196 melts 222	92	0.70	0.92	0.0732
23.	3,Cl, C ₆ H ₄ -R'	deep yellow	sint. 192 melts 242	93	0.79	0.92	0.1484
24.	4,Cl, C ₆ H ₄ -R'	yellow	sint. 198 melts 224	91	0.76	0.93	0.0566
25.	3,Cl, 2,CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₃ -R'	yellow	211-2	89	0.80	0.65	0.0705
26.	5,Cl, 2,CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₃ -R'	yellow	sint. 205	88	0.77	0.93	0.0551
27.	2,3,Cl ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R'	yellowish orange	223	86	0.78	0.93	0.0083
28.	2,4,Cl ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R'	-do-	194	91	0.80	0.93	0.0041
29.	2,5,Cl ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R'	yellow	266-8	95	0.81	0.93	0.0168
30.	2,6,Cl ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R'	dirty yellow	231-2	96	0.83	0.92	0.0083
31.	3,4,Cl ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R'	yellow	234	91	0.80	0.80	0.0532
32.	2,CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄ -R'	reddish yellow	208	95	0.80	0.96	0.0779
33.	3,CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄ -R'	light yellow	176	96	0.84	0.96	0.0389
34.	4,CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄ -R'	-do-	222-4	81	0.81	0.96	0.0778
35.	2,CH ₃ , 4,NO ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R'	deep yellow	210-5	89	0.69	0.92	0.0683
36.	4,CH ₃ , 3,NO ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R'	yellow	205-8	82	0.78	0.90	0.0383
37.	2,COOH, C ₆ H ₄ -R'	-do-	238-9 d.	91	0.58	0.91	0.0178
38.	3,COOH, C ₆ H ₄ -R'	-do-	232-4 d.	81	0.60	0.91	0.0178
39.	4,COOH, C ₆ H ₄ -R'	orangish yellow	334-5 d.	89	0.58	0.89	0.0356
40.	4,SO ₃ H, C ₆ H ₄ -R'	yellow	268	92	0.36	0.10	0.0604

⁺⁺ All the compounds gave correct nitrogen analysis.

⁼ All the melting points are uncorrected.

d. Decomposition.

^{**} Reported earlier¹.

TABLE 2—TINCTORIAL PROPERTIES OF 1-ISONICOTINOYL 3-METHYL 4-SUBSTITUTED-PHENYLazo 5-PYRAZOLONE DYES

No.	Compound	wool	silk	acetate silk	terylene	nylon
1.	C ₆ H ₅ -R ^{**}	l. yellow	l. yellow	d. yellow	d. yellow	f. yellow
2.	2,Cl, C ₆ H ₄ -R ^{**}	yellow	-do-	-do-	f. yellow	d. yellow
3.	3,Cl, C ₆ H ₄ -R'	l. yellow	-do-	yellow	l. yellow	yellow
4.	4,Cl, C ₆ H ₄ -R'	yellow	f. yellow	o. yellow	d. yellow	-do-
5.	3,Cl, 2,CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₃ -R'	-do-	l. yellow	d. yellow	-do-	d. yellow
6.	5,Cl, 2,CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₃ -R'	-do-	d. yellow	-do-	-do-	-do-
7.	2,3,Cl ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R'	-do-	l. yellow	yellow	yellow	-do-
8.	2,4,Cl ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R'	-do-	d. yellow	d. yellow	d. yellow	-do-
9.	2,5,Cl ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R'	d. yellow	l. yellow	l. yellow	yellow	-do-
10.	2,6,Cl ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R'	dirty yellow	d. yellow	-do-	—	—
11.	3,4,Cl ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R'	yellow	—	yellow	d. yellow	d. yellow
12.	2,CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄ -R'	d. yellow	l. yellow	d. yellow	l. yellow	-do-
13.	3,CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄ -R'	-do-	-do-	-do-	d. yellow	-do-
14.	4,CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄ -R'	l. yellow	-do-	yellow	yellow	yellow
15.	2,CH ₃ , 4,NO ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R'	d. yellow	d. yellow	o. yellow	o. red	d. yellow
16.	4,CH ₃ , 3,NO ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R'	-do-	l. yellow	d. yellow	d. yellow	r. yellow
17.	2,COOH, C ₆ H ₄ -R'	d. yellow	l. yellow	l. yellow	yellow	l. yellow
18.	3,COOH, C ₆ H ₄ -R'	l. yellow	l. yellow	l. yellow	—	—
19.	4,COOH, C ₆ H ₄ -R'	yellow	yellow	yellow	f. yellow	f. yellow
20.	4,SO ₃ H, C ₆ H ₄ -R'	g. yellow	—	l. yellow	—	—

^{**} Reported earlier¹.

o = orangish, d = deep, l = light, f = faint, r = reddish, g = greyish.

on various fabrics are given in table 2. With compounds numbering 17, 18, 19, (containing -COOH group), and 20 (containing -SO₃H group) the shades on the fabrics have been found much lighter. The dyed fabrics were tested for their light fastness in Atlas Colour-Fade-Ometer following standard procedures (temp., 110°F; R.H., 32-40%; intensity, 1.4 times mid-summer noon at Kanpur). Fading of the dyed wool, silk, and acetate silk fabrics were classed 5 to 6 standard, and dyed terylene and nylon 4 to 5 standard.

The fungicidal properties of pyrazolone dyes were tested on *Aspergillus niger* using Czapek medium and following dilution technique¹. The growth of fungus was examined under a microscope after 24 hrs and the amounts of the compounds in millimoles which showed complete inhibition are given in column 8, table 1.

The chromatograms of the pyrazolones as well as those of ethyl α -substituted phenylazo acetoacetate dyes were obtained using Whatman no. 1 filter papers, employing descending techniques by wooden chromatographic chambers (temp., 20° ± 1°; eluents, (1) 80% EtOH, and (2) BuOH: AcOH: H₂O :: 8:2:5). The R_f values are recorded in columns 6 and 7 of Table 1.

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Potential Antimycobacterial Agents.

I. Synthesis of N-Benzylidenediphenylamine-2 carboxylic acid hydrazides

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SINCE the advent of isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH) as a clinically effective antitubercular drug, a large number of hydrazides have been synthesised and tested for antibacterial properties¹⁻⁸. Isoxazolecarboxylic acid hydrazides have been reported as antileprotic agents⁹ and anticonvulsant activity has been described in phenothiazinecarboxylic acid hydrazides¹⁰. Hydrazones obtained from hydrazides frequently act as monoamine oxidase (MAO) inhibitors¹¹⁻¹³. Besides, hydrazides have been associated with anthelmintic¹⁴ and antifungal¹⁵ activity. In view of these observations it was felt interesting to synthesise a series of N-benzylidenehydrazides (Scheme 1) for biological screening.

SCHEME I